

A Review on Induction Motor Performance and Control Techniques in Electric Vehicles

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Abstract

Electric Vehicles (EVs) are transformative game-changer in reducing the carbon footprint in the transportation sector. To address this, a large number of researchers are attempting to determine ways to improve these EVs technologies. Identification of a suitable motor drive and the development of control schemes are essential for increased EV efficiency. This indicates that the electric motor and drive system are crucial functions, and act as the heart of the electric vehicle system. This review includes different types of electric machines and attempts to determine the most suitable one based on various operational parameters. The studies suggest that the induction motor is one of the most suitable, effective, and appropriate options for electric vehicle propulsion. Furthermore, the development of sophisticated algorithms and methodologies has led to considerable breakthroughs in the control of induction motors. Different types of control algorithms are studied. Among all field-oriented control (FOC) has shown optimal results in enhancing the effectiveness and performance of induction motors in electric vehicles. Integrating artificial intelligence techniques has optimized these control strategies, enabling real-time adaptation to changing driving conditions.

1 Introduction

Over the past decade, Electric Vehicles have transformed from a niche alternative to mainstream choices, reshaping the entire automotive landscape. Environmental impact is one of the Pivotal aspects of shifting towards EVs. Due to the burning of Hydrocarbons and harmful gases are emitted, these gases are responsible for air pollution and the greenhouse effect. Evidence suggests that one of the primary contributors of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions is urbanization and transportation [5]. Despite limits, transport remains a major contributor to global pollution, accounting for 7.7 billion metric tonnes of all CO₂ emissions by 2021. Figure 1 shows how the transportation sector contributes to CO₂ distribution in the year 2022 [6]. Moreover, passenger cars stood out as the predominant contributor, contributing 47.5 percent to the total CO₂ emissions generated within the global transportation sector [6].

Figure 1: Distribution of CO₂ emissions generated globally in 2022 by the transport sub-sector [6]

When comparing internal combustion vehicles (ICVs) with EVs it has been observed that EVs demonstrate acceptable real-life performance despite their limitations and achieve optimal results [56],[13],[44],[66]. The benefits of EVs are immense over the internal combustion engines (IC Engine) shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Comparison of EVs and ICs

Properties	IC Engine	EVs
Efficiency	Less than 50%	Up to 90%
Instant Torque	Less	More
Maintenance Required	More	Less
Regenerative Braking	No	Yes
Moving Parts	More	Less
Wear	More	Limited
Environment Friendly	No	Yes

1.1 Surveys on Electric Vehicles (EVs)

Several studies published thus far have addressed various aspects related to electric vehicles (EVs). These studies encompass a wide range of topics, including the historical evolution of EVs, classifications according to engine and design features, and analyses of their impact on the electrical infrastructure. These studies have paved the way for notable advancements over the past decade in the manufacturing and adoption of EVs, alongside the implementation of emerging technologies and their subsequent sales.

While advancements in EV manufacturing and adoption have been significant, understanding their historical context is equally important. Yong et al. [71] delve into this background, tracing the origins of EVs back to the mid-nineteenth century. As EVs have evolved from their mid-nineteenth-century origins to their modern iterations, global government subsidies have become a major factor in promoting their usage [73],[58],[37],[57].

These government initiatives are driven by a pressing need to address rising pollution levels and explore safer alternatives, with EVs emerging as a promising solution among the various options studied. The heart of an electric vehicle is its electric powertrain [33] which includes the electric motor, battery pack, and the power electronics that manage the flow of electricity between them. Just like the heart pumps blood to different body parts, the electric powertrain powers the EV, providing the necessary energy to drive the vehicle. An EV's fundamental component and brain is the electric motor that drives it. Electric motors used in automobiles must address certain requirements, including excellent power density, high efficiency, vast speed ranges, minimal torque ripple, high torque at starting, good dependability, and low weight [18]. Although each type of electric motor has advantages and disadvantages, not all are equally important for EV propulsion. Common applications for EV propulsion systems include brushed DC motors, brushless DC motor (BLDC) motors, induction motors, and permanent magnet motor (PMSM) drives.

2 Variations in Electric Vehicle Configurations and Motor Technologies

With the advancement of technology, various types of electric vehicles are becoming increasingly common, categorized based on engine technology. Typically, they are classified into five different categories as seen in Figure 2 [55].

Figure 2: Categorization of electric vehicles based on their engine technologies[55]

1. Plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEVs): PHEVs pair an externally charged electric motor with a conventional IC engine. PHEVs may store electricity from the grid because of this hybrid configuration, significantly lowering fuel consumption in everyday driving conditions [45]. For instance, the 12 kWh battery of the Mitsubishi Outlander PHEV [27] enables it to travel around 50 km on electricity alone.
2. Hybrid Electric Vehicles (HEVs) : An electric motor, as well as an IC engine, powers HEVs. A direct connection to the electrical grid is not feasible for HEVs, unlike PHEVs. On the contrary, the batteries of the electric motor are powered by the vehicle's IC engine. By transforming mechanical energy into electrical energy during braking, contemporary HEV vehicles can also be utilized to replenish their batteries. For instance, a 1.3 kWh battery

was included in the fourth-generation Toyota Prius hybrid vehicle [65], which allowed for an estimated 25 km of electric-only range.

3. Fuel Cell Electric Vehicles (FCEVs) : Compressed hydrogen and atmospheric oxygen are used by FCEVs to power their electric motors. Water is the sole output of this process. Even though FCEVs are frequently referred to in terms of "zero-emission" vehicles, it's crucial to remember that most hydrogen is obtained from natural gas, even though green hydrogen is also an option. The Hyundai Nexo, which can go 650 km before needing to be refueled, is an example of a fuel cell electric vehicle (FCEV) [30].
4. Extended-range Electric Vehicles (ER-EVs) : ER-EVs and BEVs are similar but ER-EVs are equipped with an additional combustion engine. Unlike PHEVs and HEVs, which also have engines that aid in propulsion, this engine's only function is to charge the vehicle's batteries when needed. ER-EVs are notable for not having a combustion engine attached to the wheels. One example of such a vehicle is the BMW i3 [32], which can travel 260 km on electricity and an additional 130 km in extended-range mode because of its 42.2 kWh battery. Nexo, which requires no refueling for a distance of up to 650 kilometers [30].
5. Battery Electric Vehicles (BEVs) : Electric power is the sole form of propulsion for BEVs. BEVs do not operate on liquid fuels and don't have internal combustion engines like conventional vehicles do. Usually, they need big battery packs to get a good enough range. A single charge enables a conventional BEV to cover 160–250 kilometers, while other versions can cover up to 500 kilometers. One example of this kind of car is the Tata Nexon EV [63], which has a 40.5 kWh battery that can go 465 km on a full charge.

Irrespective of Electric Vehicles all vehicles use motors according to requirements. Battery Electric Vehicles (BEVs) uniquely utilize electricity as their sole energy source. In contrast, all other vehicle types rely on some form of fuel. This distinction underscores the exclusive reliance of BEVs on electrical energy, setting them apart from other fuel-dependent vehicles. This exclusive reliance on electrical energy makes BEVs the cleanest form of vehicular technology available. Crucial Features of Electric Vehicle Traction Motors: The operational requirements for an EV traction motor are not the same as those utilized in industries. While majority of industrial loads are steady and classified, an EVs on the road must frequently adjust its speed, deliver increased torque when climbing a slope, and brake suddenly. Figure 3 illustrates a typical load profile designed for traction motors, reflecting these dynamic operational requirements [20].

It's crucial to recognize that motors seldom adhere strictly to the torque-speed curve while operating. The curves here encompass all load points. As demonstrated in Figure 3, the load cycle can be segmented into three parts based on the speed of the load cycle. The primary criteria for electrical machines used in traction consist of overload capacity, which is typically twice the engine torque rating for a brief period; compact size, lightweight, low moment of inertia, reasonable cost, fast torque response with significant power density at low speeds for starting and scaling, steady power at higher speeds, and excellent efficiency across a broad speed range with constant torque and power. Under diverse operating conditions, the vehicle's fault tolerance capabilities must be taken into account [17]. Numerous factors affect the choice of an electric vehicle motor as illustrated in Figure 4, including the vehicle's mission, the vehicle itself, its constraints, and power source variables. Vehicle constraints encompass aspects such as type of vehicle, weight, payload, and weight of the battery, while a drive cycle determines what is required of the vehicle. These factors can be considered when determining the performance criteria for an electric vehicle

Figure 3: Speed vs torque and speed vs power characteristics of Electric vehicle

by matching them with the motor's properties [34]. Figure 5 illustrates different types of motors used in EV propulsion systems. Particular requirements for the electric machines integrated into electric vehicles include greater efficiency, high-rated torque, a broad high-speed range combined with constant power, high starting torque, high power at cruising speeds, high specific power and power density, high overload capability, quick dynamic response, good flux weakening capacity at high speeds, a good fault tolerance characteristic, and high reliability. In addition, costs must be fair and competitive in the market, these specifications are essential for the different kinds of machines. Five types of motors are used in the latest vehicles: induction motors (IMs), brushed DC motors, synchronous machines, permanent magnet (PM) motors, and reluctance machines. Additional machine configurations, such as the conventional radial flux machines, have been put into use or are planned to be utilized in addition to the axial and transverse flux machines. [74],[64],[51].

Types of electric vehicle configurations implemented include:

- a) DC brushed motor;
- b) DC brushless motor (BLDC);
- c) Permanent magnet motor (PMSM);
- d) Synchronous reluctance motor (SynRM);
- e) Switched reluctance motor (SRM);
- f) Induction motor (IM);

DC brushed motor -Switching and non-switching motors are two excursion motors integrated into electric vehicles. In a nutshell, switch motors are standard DC motors with shunt and series

Figure 4: Powertrain System Integration

excitation. Because of its easy motion and torque decoupling and control, DC motors have been a subject of interest for a long time. Even now, DC motors are excellent choices for low-power applications like remote-controlled toys [51]. DC brush motors are appropriate for traction frames because they can produce large torque at low speeds. However brushed DC motors have drawbacks that render them unsuitable for use in typical electric vehicle applications, including low power density, relatively costly maintenance, and commutations. Conversely, brushless DC motors are more efficient and require less upkeep [49].

The DC motor's equations are given below

$$v = R_a \cdot I_a \cdot \frac{di_a}{dt} + E \quad (1)$$

As the field current remains constant, the flux will subsequently also remain constant, resulting in induced electromotive force (EMF) when the armature rotates,

$$E = \phi \cdot \omega \quad (2)$$

$$E = K_b \cdot \omega \quad (3)$$

Here, ω = angular velocity

K_b = back e.m.f constant.

The armature current multiplied by the magnetic flux yields the torque generated by the motor.

$$T \propto \phi \cdot i_a \quad (4)$$

$$T = K \cdot i_a \quad (5)$$

Here, K represents the torque constant of the motor.

Figure 5: Motor used in Electrical vehicle systems

The moment of inertia and coefficient of the dynamic torque equation will be represented as

$$T = J \cdot \frac{d^2\theta}{dt^2} + B \cdot \frac{d\theta}{dt} \tag{6}$$

DC brushed-less motor - The Brush-less DC (BLDC) motor is highly popular and widely used in various systems, including vehicles, boats, and home appliances, because of its compact size, the requirement of low maintenance, superior efficiency, and excellent controllability [28]. It has a stator wound with wire to keep the flux density constant and a permanent magnet rotor with a variable number of poles [67]. A permanent magnet rotor and three stator windings compose the structure of the BLDC motor. The stainless steel and magnets' high resistivity indicates that rotor-induced currents are negligible and can be ignored.

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_a \\ V_b \\ V_c \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} R & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & R & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & R \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I_a \\ I_b \\ I_c \end{bmatrix} + \frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} L_{aa} & L_{ab} & L_{ac} \\ L_{ba} & L_{bb} & L_{bc} \\ L_{ca} & L_{cb} & L_{cc} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I_a \\ I_b \\ I_c \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} e_a \\ e_b \\ e_c \end{bmatrix} \tag{7}$$

The electromagnetic torque T_e can be represented by the following equation

$$T_e = \frac{E_a I_a + E_b I_b + E_c I_c}{\omega} \tag{8}$$

The equation of the motor can be expressed, taking into consideration the load torque (represented by T_i), friction coefficient (represented by B), and inertia (represented by J).

$$T_e - T_i = J \frac{d\omega}{dt} + B\omega \tag{9}$$

Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor - The rotor in a synchronous motor rotates at synchronous speed. A DC supply powers the rotor, while an 3-phase AC supply is connected to

stator [38]. Permanent Magnet Synchronous (PMS) motors referred as brush-less AC motors, are highly efficient.

The high energy density of magnets is advantageous to PMSMs since permanent magnet agitation takes up minimal space. Within the nominal speed range, PMSMs achieve great efficiency without the requirement for excitation current. An air cooling system can efficiently reduce the iron losses in the stator, which are among the primary losses in PMSMs. Consequently, PMSMs surpass Induction Motors in terms of power density and efficiency. Numerous automobile manufacturers, such as Nissan, Honda, and Toyota, have successfully employed such motors due to their higher power density, greater efficiency, and superior heat diffusion [23]. However, the exorbitant price of rare earth magnets, like neodymium, is a significant drawback. Additionally, an extra current component for field weakening is required, leading to significant stator losses and reduced efficiency at fast speeds [16], [62].

where permanent magnet flux linkage is denoted by ψ_a .

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_a \\ v_b \\ v_c \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} R_s & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & R_s & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & R_s \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_a \\ i_b \\ i_c \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \frac{d\psi_a}{dt} \\ \frac{d\psi_b}{dt} \\ \frac{d\psi_c}{dt} \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

where: The respective phase voltages along the stator windings are v_a , v_b , and v_c . The equivalent resistance associated with each stator winding is denoted by R_s

The currents flowing through the stator windings are represented by i_a , i_b , and i_c .

$$\frac{d\psi_a}{dt}, \quad \frac{d\psi_b}{dt}, \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{d\psi_c}{dt}$$

are the rates at which each stator winding's magnetic flux changes. torque equation:

$$T = \frac{3}{2}N (i_q(i_d L_d + \psi_m) - i_d i_q L_q) \quad (11)$$

where the permanent magnet flux linkage is denoted by ψ_a .

Switched Reluctance Motors (SRM) - Rotor position switching is implemented by switched reluctance machines (SRMs) to energize the phase windings that are sequentially separated. Maintaining high speeds within the realm is possible [48]. To produce torque, the rotor seeks to move towards the location of least resistance [36]. Due to their substantial starting torque and excellent adaptability to non-critical failure capability, SRMs make sense for usage in electric vehicle applications. The steady-state activity may be shaped by the phase formation of the current in the starter's conduction edge up to the point when the coverage between the progressing phases occurs [3]. Since the SRM rotor is devoid of any kind of magnets, brushes, commutators, or windings, it is incredibly simple. With its lightweight design and low moment of inertia, this motor can operate at high speeds and accelerate quickly; its primary drawbacks are noise and torque ripple.

$$T_d = K_t \phi_f I_a \sin(\theta + \gamma) \quad (12)$$

where the torque constant is represented by k_t . For $N_1 k_{w1}$ turns, where k_{w1} is the winding factor, the rms EMF is

$$E_f \approx E_{f1} = \frac{2\pi}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\frac{\pi}{4} \cdot N_1 \right) K_{w1} f \phi_1 = k_E f \quad (13)$$

Synchronous Reluctance Motors (SynRM) - Due to its advantages—such as its straightforward and sturdy rotor structure, lack of a permanent magnet, rotor copper loss, and

the cogging torque, affordability, dependability, and high efficiency, SynRM has attracted a lot of interest lately. As a result, it has a great deal of potential to replace induction motors in EVs and other speed-driving applications [25]. SynRMs can achieve energy conversion efficiencies in the IE4 class, which is greater than IMs and just lower than PMSMs. It does, however, have certain disadvantages, the most significant of which are larger torque ripple, higher core loss, worse power factor, and trouble setting the PWM commutation instant correctly. SynRM is distinct from its IM and PMSM predecessors because of its rotor design. Because SynRM motors have very extremely less bearing and winding temperatures and no cage or Permanent magnets in the structure of rotor, they are more reliable and require less maintenance than traditional motors. Greater efficiency at the same power level within the same frame size (because of the cooler rotor operation compared to IM) [60]; greater power density and higher torque per ampere; quicker dynamic response (as a result of the reduced size at the same power level and lower moment of inertia); and a higher speed range [24]. voltage equation:

$$v_{ph} = R_s i_{ph} + \frac{\partial \lambda_{ph} di_{ph}}{\partial i_{ph} dt} + \frac{\partial \lambda_{ph} d\theta_{ph}}{\partial \theta_{ph} dt} \quad (14)$$

v_{ph} is the per-phase voltage.

R_s is the per-phase stator resistance.

i_{ph} is the per-phase current.

λ_{ph} is the flux linkage per phase.

θ_{ph} is the angle per-phase.

Instantaneous torque per phase

$$T_{ph}(i_{ph}, \theta_{ph}) = \int_0^{i_{ph}} \frac{\partial \lambda_{ph}(i_{ph}, \theta_{ph})}{\partial \theta_{ph}} di_{ph} \quad (15)$$

Induction Motor - Induction motors are commonly utilized in industrial applications and electric traction owing to their cost-effectiveness and durability. Electric vehicles typically employ induction motors because of their significant efficiency, reliability, robustness, low cost, superb speed control, and non-commutation. For electric vehicles, an induction motor drive is ideal. Since they are the least dialed switch, they are now widely recognized. Their great dependability and low maintenance requirements can be attributed to this [15]. A vector-control drive is usually used to operate induction motors since it allows for a large speed range fluctuation. As Figure 6 illustrates, induction machines have three distinct regions of operation, (a) a region of constant torque, (b) a region of constant power, and (c) a region of reduced power when reaching high speeds. These features result from the design of the machine, power electronics, and control systems [52],[1]. The normal power, torque, and speed characteristics match those needed for the electrical traction system.

$$V_a = R_a \cdot I_a + L_a \frac{di_a}{dt} + e_a \quad (16)$$

$$V_b = R_b \cdot I_b + L_b \frac{di_b}{dt} + e_b \quad (17)$$

$$V_c = R_c \cdot I_c + L_c \frac{di_c}{dt} + e_c \quad (18)$$

Figure 6: Torque-speed characteristics of induction motor

Due to their extraordinary efficiency, exceptional speed regulation, and absence of a commutator, three-phase induction motors are an excellent choice for electric vehicles. A three-phase AC supply powers the stator winding, creating a rotating magnetic field. AC induction motor drives are ideally suited for use in EVs. They are widely acknowledged today for their commutator-less design. This explains their high reliability and minimal maintenance needs. Vector Control, a strategy aimed at enhancing the dynamic response of the electric drive system, can also be implemented in this context. Vector Control enables a wide speed range beyond the base speed, offering high efficiency with a rapid and resilient response to changes in speed or torque [46]. The device all in all is low accelerated, which diminishes unwavering quality and productivity. However, in comparison with families of PMAC motors, they exhibit greater rotor inertia, increased torque ripple, lower power, and torque densities, resulting in reduced speed dynamic response [19]

From the manufacturer's standpoint, the most popular motors are PMSM, BLDC, and induction. Induction motors (IMs) stand out due to their brushless design, eliminating maintenance needs and sparking hazards associated with Brushed DC motors. They offer superior efficiency across varying speeds and boast excellent cooling and thermal management capabilities, along with higher power and torque densities essential for EV performance demands. Compared to Brushless DC (BLDC) motors, IMs are more cost-effective due to simpler construction and reduced reliance on expensive rare-earth magnets. They excel in industrial environments, providing durability and ease of control without complex electronics, which lowers operational costs. Additionally, IMs surpass Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motors (PMSMs) in cost-effectiveness, resilience in high temperatures, and capacity to handle higher loads without performance decline. In conclusion, IMs represent the optimal choice for EV propulsion systems, combining efficiency, reliability, and cost-effectiveness

to meet stringent performance requirements while advancing sustainable electric mobility. Their continuous evolution highlights their crucial importance in defining the future trajectory of EVs.

Using ten performance metrics for motor, each scored up to ten points, totaling one hundred points, Figure 7 outlines the comprehensive performance comparison between IMs drives and other electric motors used in different propulsion systems of EVs [72].

Figure 7: Electric motor performance comparison, scored out of 100 [74]

Higher values indicate better performance. Based on all parameters, including cost and thermal management, Induction motor drive stands out as the optimal choice for top-tier electric vehicles, according to the study. Table 2 depicts the essential characteristics of various types of motor.

Table 2: Analyzing the essential characteristics of various motor types

Characteristics	DC	IM	PM	SRM
Power density	Low	Medium	Very high	Medium
Efficiency	Low	Medium	Very high	Medium
Controllability	Very high	Very high	High	Medium
Reliability	Medium	Very high	High	Very high
Technological maturity	Very high	Very high	High	High
Cost	Low	Very low	High	Low

3 Control Schemes for Induction Motors

3.0.1 Scalar Control (SC)

This is the first method for controlling electrical machinery that was created: scalar control [41]. It is used to regulate the motor’s speed in relation to the frequency and amplitude of the applied voltage. The induction motor’s permanent state modeling serves as the foundation for its theory.

For the V/f ratio to remain constant and the capacity of torque to be maximised, the flux needs to be kept within a large range that is equivalent to its nominal value C_{\max} . Several studies have revealed that Scalar Control (SC) regulates the speed of Induction Motors (IM). In [7], a five-leg voltage source inverter was utilized to drive dual single-phase IMs via a Closed-loop technique for regulating scalar V/f speed. The experimental findings demonstrated that the system implemented can independently control each motor's maintenance of constant speed under a range of operating conditions.

3.0.2 Direct Torque Control (DTC)

Direct Torque Control (DTC), a control technique employed by induction motors, directly manages both torque and flux without requiring the complex coordinate transformations used in Field-Oriented Control (FOC). It achieves this by continuously comparing the actual and desired torque and flux values, and adjusting the voltage vectors applied to the motor accordingly. This is how torque and flux are directly controlled. It is divided into two categories (1) Direct Self-Control (DSC), established in 1986 by Takashi and Noguchi [61] and Direct Self-Control (DSC) established in 1988 by Depenbrock [9]. The torque control approach in Direct Self-Control (DSC) entails modifying the stator flux's rotating speed along a hexagonal trajectory. Direct Torque Control (DTC), on the other hand, controls the stator flux in the trajectory of a circular while keeping it constant in space. Current harmonics at the inverter terminals expand as the consequence of the stator flux trajectory similar to DTC [35]. However, these higher current harmonics elevate the temperature of Induction Motor windings, thereby reducing the drive system's lifespan [42]. The values of stator flux Ψ_s and electromagnetic torque T_{em} are compared to their respective reference values, T_{em}^* and Ψ_s^* . The hysteresis comparators take inputs from the comparison results. T_{em}^* and Ψ_s^* , the reference values for stator flux and electromagnetic torque, respectively, are compared with the estimated values. The comparison results enter the hysteresis comparators as inputs. The electromagnetic torque is regulated through a three-level hysteresis comparator. A comparator with two levels of hysteresis is employed to regulate the flux of the stator. Direct torque control is fast, durable, and simple, but it has two significant disadvantages. Two factors are present in the considered operation: (a) the switching frequency is highly variable, and (b) the torque and stator flux ripple amplitude is not well regulated throughout the entire speed range [59], [14]. Indeed, a relatively short sample time and, as a result, a highly variable switching frequency is needed to practically implement nonlinear features of the hysteresis type. Inverter switches experience increased losses and limitations as a result of this operation [12]. Neglecting the stator resistance also leads to issues at low speeds.

3.0.3 Field Oriented Control (FOC)

In response to the limitations of Scalar control, field-oriented control of the IM was designed to handle applications with medium-to-high dynamic and static performance. IM model projected in the flux reference frame served as the basis for this control, which was first proposed in 1972. The control attempts to achieve a performance of IM similar to an independently stimulated DC machine in which the torque and flux are decoupled [68]. The components resulting from the direct and quadrature axes of the stator current enable decoupled control of torque and flux in both dynamic and steady-state conditions. This decoupling offers excellent efficiency throughout a broader load range and a wide range of speed control. Three distinct vector control techniques can be identified

based on the orientation angle or flux position angle: sensorless vector control, indirect vector control, and direct vector control.

These methods are referred to as direct if the angle is directly obtainable from the two-phase components of the flux; if not, they are considered indirect. The integral of the stator pulsation can be obtained by deriving it from the linear combination of the rotor speed and the slip pulsation, which can be used to calculate the angle [8],[47]. Thus, it should be emphasized that direct approaches need a flux sensor or its estimation, whereas indirect methods need a velocity sensor or its estimation. However, a lot of researchers have chosen indirect flux vector control since it doesn't require flux measurement devices because it can estimate the rotor flux from recorded currents and speeds. [50]. To execute the control commands in the FOC technique, the controller needs feedback signals from sensors measuring voltage, rotor speed, and current. As a result, signals from the sensor, particularly the stator currents, play a critical role in the control mechanism of the induction motor drive (IMD) system. If any sensor malfunctions, the IMD system can become inoperative. Consequently, it is recommended that sensorless control (SLC) be employed to enhance the operation of IM drives [21]. In recent times, researchers have developed an interest in the CSL approach. Numerous studies have been published on this topic. It is suggested in the study by [69] to estimate state variables using the measured rotor speed signal and DC-link current. The reference current and estimated current are calculated using two separate loops, and the control voltage in the current controller is then determined using the PI controllers. The simulation results demonstrate satisfactory performance across the medium-speed spectrum.

A comparison between Field-Oriented Control (FOC), Direct Torque Control (DTC), and Scalar Control for induction motors highlights the advantages of FOC, emphasizing its benefits. Scalar Control (SC) is the simplest method for controlling induction motors. It adjusts the voltage and frequency proportionally to control the speed but lacks precise control over torque and flux, leading to poor dynamic performance and inefficiency under varying load conditions. Direct Torque Control (DTC) offers a more sophisticated approach by directly controlling the torque and flux through hysteresis controllers. While it provides a better dynamic response compared to SC, DTC can result in high torque and flux ripples due to its discrete nature. These ripples can cause increased acoustic noise and mechanical stress on the motor. Field-oriented control (FOC), also denoted by vector control, surpasses both SC and DTC by converting the stator currents to a rotating reference frame. This transformation allows for the independent control of flux and torque-producing components. As a result, FOC provides smoother and more accurate control, leading to higher efficiency and better performance under dynamic conditions.

With advancements in technology, FOC has been further enhanced by incorporating various sophisticated algorithms listed below.

4 FOC based on Artificial Intelligence techniques

In power electronics and electrical machine control, artificial intelligence methods like Fuzzy Logic (FL), Genetic Algorithms (GA), and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) have been extensively used to improve the dynamic performance of Field-Oriented Control (FOC).

4.1 Fuzzy Logic (FL)

Fuzzy logic, and broader techniques for managing uncertainty, represent significant classes within artificial intelligence. These methods excel in situations where conventional binary logic struggles

to provide precise decisions due to ambiguous or incomplete information. By allowing for degrees of truth rather than strict true or false outcomes, fuzzy logic enables more nuanced decision-making processes. This capability has found wide application in various fields, including control systems, where it enhances adaptability and robustness in dealing with real-world complexities and uncertainties [2]. A fuzzy logic controller was incorporated within the FOC for the seven-phase IM for a hybrid electric vehicle (HEV) system by the authors of [31]. The fuzzy logic controller, based on the results, minimized parasitic currents and decreased leakage and losses. A further application of the artificial neural network (ANN) method has been to enhance the functionality of traditional FOC. Over 90% of the torque and flux ripple reduction was achieved by utilizing fuzzy logic duty cycle controllers and switching controllers incorporating fuzzy logic [53]. As neural networks can approximate functions universally, the suggested technique outperforms the base speed estimation of the Model Reference Adaptive System (MRAS) in terms of computational complexity and yields superior results [22].

4.2 Artificial Neural Network (ANN)

In the paper [70], the authors suggest modifying the FOC vector method by substituting ANN-based controllers for conventional PI controllers to increase the reliability and quality of electric drive systems. The simulation results validated the accuracy of the model created using the ANN-FOC technique. When ANN-based hysteresis comparators are used in place of traditional ones, as demonstrated in [10], the benefits of torque and flux ripple reduction, rapid and precise speed monitoring, and other advantages are demonstrated. With high dynamic performance, ANN control also lowers the total harmonic distortion (THD) of the induction motor's stator voltage and current. Consequently, for the direct FOC of a three-phase asynchronous motor, [11] develops an adaptive predictive current controller (APCC). When compared with the standard hysteresis current controller, the controller has proven to be efficient in terms of rapid dynamics, improved decoupling, high tolerance to stator resistance, load fluctuations, and enhanced speed tracking. The [26], demonstrated a sophisticated FOC with with no requirement for current sensors. The proposed approach employs differential equations using the stator and rotor current state variables to estimate current within the FOC loop. The outcomes indicated effective speed control could be achieved using FOC methods without a current sensor.

4.3 Genetic Algorithm

Genetic algorithms (GA) are a diverse and intriguing set of algorithms used for stochastic optimization. Inspired by natural evolution, GAs can effectively analyze large search spaces and identify multiple solutions to a given problem [40]. They can provide excellent solutions for a wide range of issues with relatively low computational effort and time investment [43]. In this research, the study focuses on the problem of identification of parameters for the field orientation control (FOC) of induction motors using genetic algorithms (GAs). The results show that the GA approach outperforms a simple random search strategy and that the improved model significantly increases parameter identification accuracy. The GA is a potent tool for parameter identification, it is concluded. [29] The use of genetic algorithms (GAs) as a substitute method for controller optimization is currently dominating research on driving high-performance electric machines.

To Surmount the drawbacks of the field-oriented control (FOC) strategy, the hybrid fuzzy-fuzzy controller (HFFC) has been proposed. The study investigates the efficacy of HFFC in regulating

speed within a variable-speed induction motor (IM) drive system. According to simulation outcomes, both the conventional hybrid fuzzy-PI controller (HFPI) and the HFFC with GA optimization were found to be less effective strategies for IM speed control compared to the non-GA optimized HFFC[39]. In recent research focusing on controlling advanced electric machines, genetic algorithms (GAs) have emerged as an alternative technique for optimizing PI controllers [4] [54]. Based on the simulation results, the GA torque controller demonstrates superior performance compared to both the PI and ANN controllers, characterized by lower energy consumption and reduced torque ripple, particularly at higher speeds.

4.4 Comparative Evaluation And Critical Technique

We offer an analysis of the performance of many induction motor management techniques with respect to torque and flux ripple, algorithm complexity, parameter sensitivity, dynamic response, switching frequency, and current harmonic distortion. Based on this study, it can be said that the FOC control has solved every issue with the CS and DTC controls, particularly the latter's extreme sensitivity to machine parameter changes. Artificial intelligence techniques are among the proposed control strategies aimed at achieving lower torque ripple and reduced switching frequency at identical sampling frequencies. Table 3 describes the performance of various control techniques. But they come at a significant cost in terms of complexity. As a result, it can be used in high-power applications for highly precise control. To minimize energy losses, Field-Oriented Control (FOC) can be effectively applied in electric vehicles, renewable energy conversion systems, and the industrial sector.

Table 3: Comparison of Control Techniques for Induction Motors

Methods Performance	Scalar Control	FOC	Standard DTC	Fuzzy based FOC	ANN based FOC	GA based FOC
Performance in Transient State	Minimal	Medium	High	High	High	High
Torque and Flux Ripple	Low	Medium	High	Minimal	Minimal	Medium
Switching frequency	Nearly Constant	Nearly Constant	Variable	Stable	Stable	Stable
Parameter Sensitivity	High Sensitive	High Sensitive	Insensitive	Less sensitive	Less sensitive	Less sensitive
Dynamic Response of Torque	Fast	Fast	Rapid	Rapid	Rapid	Rapid
Harmonic Distortion of Current	Minimum distortion	Less distortion	More distortion	Less distortion	Less distortion	Less distortion
Complexity of Algorithm	Very Simple	Complex	More complex	More complex	Complex	Complex

5 Conclusion

Based on extensive analysis and empirical studies, induction motors (IMs) emerge as the optimal choice for electric vehicles (EVs), distinguished by their robustness, reliability, and efficiency.

Unlike brushed DC motors, IMs operate without brushes, ensuring reduced maintenance and eliminating sparking hazards, which is critical for automotive and industrial applications. Their straightforward yet durable design ensures consistent performance under varying conditions, making them economically viable for mass production. Field-Oriented Control (FOC) stands out as the superior control strategy for IMs, particularly in applications requiring high performance. Unlike Scalar Control (SC) and Direct Torque Control (DTC), FOC excels by decoupling torque and flux components through a transformation into a rotating reference frame aligned with the rotor flux. This precision enables independent regulation of motor operations, minimizing energy losses and optimizing efficiency across diverse load conditions. FOC's ability to mitigate torque ripple enhances motor reliability and longevity, making it well-suited for EVs, industrial machinery, and renewable energy systems. Furthermore, the integration of advanced algorithms such as Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Genetic Algorithms (GA), and Fuzzy Logic enhances FOC's adaptability and performance in dynamic operational environments. As an established industry standard, FOC continues to drive advancements in motor efficiency and operational flexibility, significantly contributing to the evolution of sustainable electric propulsion technologies.

In conclusion, IMs with FOC represents a compelling solution for achieving high efficiency, reliability, and performance in modern electric vehicles and industrial applications alike. This combination not only meets but exceeds the stringent demands of today's electric mobility and industrial sectors, setting a benchmark for technological innovation and sustainable development in the global drive towards electrification.

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